

Complexes of 2-Methoxy-4-amino-5-chloro-*N*-[2-(diethylamino)ethyl]benzamide with Metal Ions

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The complexes of 2-methoxy-4-amino-5-chloro-*N*-[2-(diethylamino)ethyl]benzamide (L) with the metal ions of the types ML_2X_4 ($M = Ni^{II}, Cd^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II}$ and Zn^{II} ; $X = \frac{1}{2}SO_4^{2-}, Cl^-$ or NO_3^-), ML_2X_6 ($M = Cu^{II}$), MLX_4 ($M = Pd^{II}$) and $MLX(M = Ag^I)$ have been isolated and characterised on the basis of their elemental analyses, magnetic, molar conductance, ir and electronic spectral studies. The ML_2X_4 and MLX_4 complexes are square planar, while ML_2X_6 complexes are octahedral. The MLX complex is probably bridging one. Only the $Pd^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}$ and Ag^I complexes are diamagnetic, while the others are paramagnetic. They all are electrolytes except the Pd^{II} complex, which is non-electrolyte.

A perusal of literature shows that much more is known about pharmacological activity of 2-methoxy-4-amino-5-chloro-*N*-[2-(diethylamino)ethyl]benzamide but nothing is reported about its ligational character or analytical applicability. The author observes that it contains a system analogous to that present in 'en'^{1,2} which is a bidentate ligand and forms complexes with numerous metal ions. Many of them have been resolved by Werner³⁻⁵. So the present ligand may also be expected to behave accordingly and in fact, it has been found so. Thus the author has simply introduced it as a new ligand of known system, explored the methods of isolation of its complexes with $Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Pd^{II}, Fe^{II}, Mn^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}$ and Ag^I and characterised with a view that these complexes might have biological importance.

Experimental

The ligand under study was of IPCA grade, and all the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Standard solutions (0.01M) of the metals and ligand were prepared in redistilled water. Only palladium was used in dilute HCl.

Preparation of complexes: The $Ni^{II}, Cd^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II}$ and Zn^{II} complexes were prepared separately by treating the solutions of the metals with reagent in 1:3 molar ratio, adding a few drops of 2M NH_4OH solution and crystallising on water-bath. The Cu^{II} complex was formed by reacting the solution of the metal with reagent in 1:2 molar ratio in presence of a little 2M NaOH solution and digesting on the water-bath. The Ag^I and Pd^{II} complexes were formed by

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Complexes	pH	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff} B.M.	ΔM $\Omega^{-1}cm^2$	λ_{max} cm^{-1}
			M	C	H	N			
NiL_2SO_4	7.5	Blue	5.56 (5.57)	47.80 (47.83)	6.22 (6.36)	11.90 (11.90)	2.9	118.36	11 500, 19 000, 39 500
FeL_2SO_4	6.0	Dirty green	5.29 (5.29)	47.88 (47.96)	6.24 (6.28)	11.91 (11.99)	5.4	160.25	10 600, 12 000
$CoL_2(NO_3)_2$	7.5	Pale pink	5.44 (5.45)	49.50 (49.60)	6.02 (6.10)	14.19 (14.24)	4.8	188.25	9 000, 20 500, 23 500
MnL_2Cl_2	6.5	Yellowish pink	5.35 (5.36)	49.10 (49.19)	6.40 (6.44)	12.20 (12.29)	5.9	192.45	18 000, 23 000, 25 200, 28 000, 30 100, 32 600
ZnL_2Cl_2	7.0	White	6.30 (6.31)	48.68 (48.70)	6.30 (6.37)	12.11 (12.17)	—	193.40	—
$CdL_2(NO_3)_2$	7.5	White	9.80 (9.90)	44.37 (44.40)	5.37 (5.81)	13.50 (13.56)	—	201.50	—
CuL_2SO_4	6.5	Blue	8.20 (8.38)	44.20 (44.29)	5.75 (5.80)	16.54 (16.61)	2.1	163.35	15 800, 18 500
$PdLCl_2$	3.5	Yellow	22.22 (22.24)	35.10 (35.29)	4.56 (4.60)	8.78 (8.81)	0.0	1.80	500, 29 760
$AgLNO_3$	3.0	Yellow	22.80 (22.98)	35.00 (35.75)	4.60 (4.60)	8.80 (8.93)	—	10.10	—

treating the solutions of these metals with reagent in 1 : 1 molar ratio and then adding 2 M HNO₃ and NH₄OH solutions, respectively. The complexes were filtered, washed with water and dried in air, except the Ag^I, Fe^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes which were dried in vacuum.

Results and Discussion

The colour, analytical, magnetic moment, molar conductance and electronic spectral data of the complexes are incorporated in Table 1. The Ag^I complex upon treatment with dilute NH₄OH turns to white and then grey. The Fe^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes are oxidised to brown masses in air. The blue colour of the Co^{II} complex turns gradually to pale pink when kept unfiltered with supernatant liquid for 3-4 days. The colour change may be attributed to the replacement of ligand molecules with water or formation of a complex of indefinite composition.

Molar conductance: Very low molar conductance of the Pd^{II} complex shows it to be a non-electrolyte, while the other complexes are electrolytes.

Magnetic moment: The Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Ag^I complexes are usually diamagnetic (nd¹⁰ electronic system). On the spin-pair assumption of the d⁸ electrons in Pd^{II} which leads to b_{2g}²e_g⁴a_{1g}² (S=0) suggests it to be diamagnetic and square planar. Magnetic moments (Table 1) indicate that the Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Fe^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes contain 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 unpaired electrons, respectively to account for paramagnetism. The magnetic moments of the Ni^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes are found very close to their spin-only values. Naturally, orbital contributions are quenched in them by the crystal-line ligand field. However, the moments of the Fe^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are pretty above their spin-only values. Appreciable orbital contribution appears in them. The moments indicate that they are octahedral, except the Cu^{II} complex.

Electronic spectra: The absorption peaks at 11 500, 19 000 and 20 500 cm⁻¹ in the Ni^{II} complex resemble with those found in Ni(en)₃²⁺ and are consistent with the octahedral geometry. They may be assigned to the transitions from ³A_{2g} (F) to ³T_{2g} (F), ³T_{1g} (F) and ³T_{1g} (F), respectively. Further, Dq=1 150 cm⁻¹, B (peak intercept on Y-axis)=904 cm⁻¹, ν₈/ν₂=1.6 and β=0.83 support the O_h symmetry. Also a weak s-f band at 17 200 cm⁻¹ favours the same. The peaks at 9 000, 20 590 and 23 500 cm⁻¹ in the Co^{II} complex, assignable to the transitions from ⁴T_{1g} to ⁴T_{2g} (F), ⁴A_{2g} (F) and ⁴T_{1g} (F), respectively and also the various electronic parameters, i.e. Dq=900 cm⁻¹, B=937 cm⁻¹, ν₈/ν₁=2.61 and β=0.83 suggest the octahedral structure. A single band at 10 600 cm⁻¹, separated with another peak at 12 000 cm⁻¹ in the Fe^{II} complex favours its octahedral geometry. The 10 600 cm⁻¹

band may be assigned to ⁵T_{2g}→⁵E_g transition. Dq=1 060 cm⁻¹, B=530 cm⁻¹ and β=0.50 also favour O_h symmetry of the complex. Six closely spaced but distinct bands at 19 000, 23 000, 25 200, 28 000, 30 100 and 32 600 cm⁻¹ in the Mn^{II} complex suggest its octahedral structure. They may be assigned to the transitions from ⁶A_{1g} to ⁴T₁ (G), ⁴T_{2g} (G), ⁴A_{1g} (G), ⁴T_{2g} (D), ⁴E_g (D) and ⁴T_{1g} (P), respectively. Non-broadening of the bands due to vibronic coupling has been explained earlier. B=775 cm⁻¹, ν₈/ν₁=1.7 and β=0.80 also favour the O_h symmetry of the complex. The Cu^{II} complex exhibits bands at 15 800 and 18 500 cm⁻¹, assignable to ²B_{1g}→²A_{1g} and ²B_{1g}→²E_g transitions, and may be inferred to possess D_{4h} symmetry. Further, the band at 15 800 cm⁻¹ accounts for its blue colour. The bands at 23 500 and 29 760 cm⁻¹ in the Pd^{II} complex shows D_{4h} symmetry and they may be assigned to transitions from ¹A_{1g} to ¹B_{1g} and ¹E_g.

Infrared spectra: Only a few ir bands have been discussed. The ligand contains the system, $\begin{matrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ | & | & | & | \\ -N-C-C-N- < \end{matrix}$. Nitrogen atom of the end groups (1,4-positions) behave as the main binding sites. In the ir spectrum of the ligand, several medium and sharp bands at 2920, 2910-2 890, 1 680, 1 600, 1 590 and 750 may be assigned to ν_{C-H} saturated, ν_{CH₂} or ν_{CH}, ν_{C=O} or amide I, ring skeletal vibration, ν_{N-CO} or ν_{CN} + ν_{C=O} and ν_{C-Cl}, respectively remain unchanged in the complexes. The band at 1 550 cm⁻¹, assigned to amide II frequency, shifts downward to 1 510 cm⁻¹ and two bands at 3 350 and 3 280 cm⁻¹ which are characteristics of non-cyclic secondary amide NH also show negative shift to single band at 3 220-3 207 cm⁻¹. They indicate that coordination takes place through imino nitrogen (NH) or amide II. Modification of intensity in some complexes is merely due to strong M-N bonding. Das and Rao⁶ suggested ν_{NH} at 3 300-3 280 and 3 240-3 170 cm⁻¹ in the propylene complexes with Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}. Out of several bands appearing in the range 3 050-2 810 cm⁻¹ in the free ligand, the sharp one which appears at 2 810 cm⁻¹ may be attributed to ν_{N(CH₂)} or a combination of ν_{CH₂} and ν_{N(NH₂)}. Further, the bands at 1 480 and 1 430 cm⁻¹ in the ligand may be assigned to ν_{C-N} and ν_{N(CH₂)₂}, respectively. These bands also show negative shifts to 2 760-2 745, 1 460-1 450 and 1 390-1380 cm⁻¹ in the complexes showing that tertiary nitrogen of N(C₃H₇)₂ participates in the coordination to the metal ions. The fact is further supported⁷ by ν_{M-N} at 475-425 cm⁻¹. Murthy and Lingaiah⁸ reported ν_{M-N} at still lower frequencies, i.e. at 390-360 cm⁻¹ in benzimidazole complexes with metal ions. The sharp bands at 1 379-1 365 cm⁻¹ in the Co^{II}, Cd^{II} and Ag^I complexes may be attributed to NO₃⁻, while bands at 1 125-1 120

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where, $\phi = \text{C}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NH}_2)(\text{OCH}_3)\text{Cl}-$, $\text{M} = \text{Ni}^{2+}$, Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ; $\text{X} = \frac{1}{2}\text{SO}_4^{2-}$, NO_3^- or Cl^- .

cm^{-1} in the Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Fe^{2+} complexes suggest the presence of SO_4^{2-} . The medium sharp band at 280 cm^{-1} in the Pd^{2+} complex suggests that Cl^- lies inside the coordination sphere. But no clear bands for ionic chlorine is found in the spectra of the Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} complexes. The CH_2 rocking mode is found at 755 cm^{-1} in all the complexes probably due to cyclisation of system in ligand under the influence of steric hindrance and inter-ligand repulsion. Thus, the above tentative structures of the complexes may be proposed.

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